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Conference Proceedings

Editor
DR. DANIEL BIGGS

Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health

2nd June 2025

Academy of Sport and Wellbeing

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The Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health is a celebration and recognition of UHI Perth's student work throughout the academic year 2024-2025. This event showcases poster presentations spanning from Higher National Certificates at level 7 to Fourth Year Undergraduate Degrees at level 10. The posters and slides feature research based on Graded Units, Work Placements and Dissertations, highlighting the academic achievements and innovative contributions of our students in the fields of Sport, Health and Outdoor Education.

Student Conference Committee

Chair – Dr. Daniel Biggs

Programme Leader - BSc (Hons) Sports Therapy and Rehabilitation
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Senior Committee Member - Dagmara Dabrowska-Kochanek
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Committee Member – Sofiiia Chervonnaia
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Student in Higher National Certificate: Soft Tissue Therapy

Conference Proceedings Editor – Dr. Daniel Biggs

UHI Perth
Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health
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The Thematic Statement of the Student Conference

The Power of Health and Sport Students

Health and sport students in the UK are not just preparing for future careers, they are already making a significant impact across education, industry, and public wellbeing. As the health and sport sectors rapidly evolve, our students bring a unique combination of energy, adaptability, and evidence-based thinking that drives progress and innovation.

The UK faces growing challenges, for example physical inactivity costs the NHS above an estimated £700 million each year (Heron, 2021), and 1 in 10 young people in Scotland now experience a mental illness (Children's and Young Peoples Commissioner Scotland, 2020). Health and sport students are supporting these issues by developing and assisting new interventions, supporting mental health initiatives, and applying their knowledge to improve wellbeing and physical activity across various sectors.

The student involvement in placements and applied projects also benefits the industry. Fleming, Ferns, Zegwaard (2023) discuss student placements can increase work capacity, impact workplace culture, enhanced recruitment, provide opportunities for staff development, provide connection with educational institutions, and further company altruistic values. Thus, whether delivering strength and conditioning plans, supporting rehabilitation services, promoting mental wellbeing, or using performance analytics, students contribute a meaningful value to organisations from day one.

At the same time, these experiences equip students with essential professional skills such as teamwork, critical thinking, communication, and real-life practice making them workforce-ready and deeply connected to real-world needs. Furthermore, student curiosity and drive also inspire those around them, often influencing the direction of projects, services, community engagement and deepen reflective practice in placement mentors.

Therefore, health and sport students are not just the future of their fields, they are co-creators of present-day progress. With the right support and opportunities, student contribution will continue to shape a more active, healthy, and responsive UK society.

Reference List

Children's and Young People's Commissioner Scotland (2020) *Mental health*. Available at: <https://www.cypcs.org.uk/positions/mental-health-2>

Fleming, J., Ferns, S.J. and Zegwaard, K.E. (2023) 'Benefits of work-integrated learning for host organizations', *The Routledge international handbook of work-integrated learning*. London: Routledge, pp. 113–130.

Heron, L. (2021) *The health economics of physical inactivity and sedentary behaviour: healthcare expenditure and cost-effective interventions*. PhD thesis. Queen's University Belfast.

Student Conference Attendee Task: Synthesis of Research

Task:

Formulate a question that can be answered using findings from *three* or more poster presentations.

Detailed Activity Plan:

a) Forming Groups

- Students to work individually, in pairs, or in groups of three.

b) Poster Review

- Each group or individual reviews all posters, remembering key findings, themes, and interesting points.
- Encourage students to engage with the poster authors to gain deeper insights and clarifications.

c) Question Formulation

- Groups think to formulate a single question that can be answered by integrating elements from at least three reviewed posters.
- Students are encouraged to identify common themes, contrasting results, or complementary findings.

d) Wrap-Up

- Groups feedback to the larger group on what question they pose with an answer guided by the combination of three or more poster findings.

Skills developed from the task:

Critical Thinking: Analysing information from multiple sources and synthesising it into a cohesive question.

Creativity and Innovation: Generating unique ideas from multiple sources and perspectives.

Collaboration and Teamwork: Working effectively in groups to communicate ideas and build on each other's contributions.

Lateral Thinking: Connecting contrasting pieces of research to develop a question.

Efficacy of strength training on flexibility and cardiovascular endurance on a young adult

Sofia Chervonnaia
University of Highlands and Islands

Purpose

The aim of this project was to investigate the components of strength training and identify the impact on flexibility and cardiovascular endurance in young adults.

Introduction

This project will involve a 12-week individualised programme, designed for a 32-year-old male who used to be an athlete and played handball for almost 15 years. The client will be tested for overall health and fitness before the start of the programme, by the end of 6th week (midpoint testing) and at the end of 12th week of the programme. Tests will involve health screening and fitness tests regarding overall strength, cardiovascular endurance and flexibility.

The programme did not involve any type of cardiovascular endurance or flexibility training apart from dynamic stretching in the beginning as a part of a warm-up and static stretching in the end of the session in order to maintain flexibility levels the client already had. According to Júnior *et al* (2011), flexibility levels can be improved performing strength training only regardless of number of sets performed during training sessions. Regarding the impact strength training has on cardiovascular endurance, according to Hoff *et al* (2002) maximal strength training enhances not only strength, but also aerobic endurance when strength training is focused on adaptation to the load

Name of the test	Pre-programme test result	Midpoint test result (6 weeks in)	Final test result (the end of 12 th week)
1RM	Back Squat – 120kg	Back Squat – 120kg	Back Squat – 122kg
	Lat pulldown – 84.5kg	Lat pulldown – 84.5kg	Lat pulldown – 89kg
1,5 Mile Run	10.18 minutes	12.10 minutes	10.16 minutes
Hand grip dynamometer	L arm – 36kg	L arm – 47.7kg	L arm – 47.5kg
	R arm – 44kg	R arm – 50kg	R arm – 49kg
Sit and Reach	+13cm	+6cm	+5cm
Back scratch	L arm – -22cm	L arm – -22cm	L arm – -4cm
	R arm – -11.5cm	R arm – -11.5cm	R arm – -11cm

Name of the test	Pre-programme test result	Midpoint test result (6 weeks in)	Final test result (the end of 12 th week)
Body Mass Index (BMI)	25.1	25.2	25.1
Waist-to-hip ratio	0.75	0.8	0.8
Limb girth	L Quadricep – 52cm	L Quadricep – 52cm	L Quadricep – 56cm
	R Quadricep – 52cm	R Quadricep – 52cm	R Quadricep – 56cm
Body fat percentage	24.4%	23.6%	24.3%
Resting heart rate /Blood pressure	RHR – 66	RHR – 68	RHR – 64
	BP – 123	BP – 106	BP – 103
Peak flow	720	650	670

Discussion & Conclusion

Throughout the 12-week intervention, the client made progressions regarding strength and volume increase, however during the completion of the programme there were adjustments made on multiple occasions regarding the training programme.

In conclusion, the project is considered to be successful – the client's and project's aims and objectives were met. The client showed significant improvements regarding strength and flexibility, which determined that strength training has an impact on flexibility levels. And even though strength training has been shown to have a positive effect on cardiovascular endurance, this project did not identify significant improvements as a result of performing strength training only. In order to identify how strength training might impact cardiovascular endurance, further investigation is required.

Hoff, J., Gran, A., & Helgerud, J. (2002). Maximal strength training improves aerobic endurance performance. *Scandinavian journal of medicine & science in sports*, 12(5), 288-295.

Júnior, R., Leite, T. and Reis, V., (2011) Influence of the number of sets at a strength training in the flexibility gains. *Journal of human kinetics*, 29, pp.47-52.

Introduction

In this report, the author investigated the clinical difference in effectiveness between Manual Clinical Massage Therapy and Deep Tissue Massage Gun Techniques on Delayed Onset Muscle Soreness. Furthermore, this report will establish if any one type of treatment is more effective compared to the other at alleviating the symptoms of DOMS and aiding in the recovery process, therefore enabling individuals to return to further exercise and physical activity.

Objectives

Objective 1 - To outline the techniques involved with both variations of massage therapy and determine if there is an optimal treatment from either or both techniques.

Objective 2 - To use secondary sources in the form of journal articles, peer-reviewed studies and relevant books throughout the process to ensure that during the investigation all qualitative and quantifiable data is legitimate and accurately reflects the aims set out, which will be to establish if one or both techniques are optimal for individuals experiencing DOMS.

Objective 3 - Come to a credible conclusion regarding both techniques, weighing up both the benefits and possible drawbacks of one or both techniques.

Results

Ferria et al. (2023) found that massage guns improve flexibility and range of motion (ROM), especially in the posterior muscle chain, after just 2 minutes of use. Low-frequency (29 Hz) treatments reduced muscle stiffness more effectively than manual therapy; however, the long-term benefits are still unclear. Longer sessions at low frequencies may also reduce soreness (DOMS).

Greene et al. (2024) also showed that massage guns boost ROM and tissue flexibility shortly after use, aiding injury prevention and athletic recovery. Percussive massage has been shown to help reduce muscle soreness 24-72 hours after exercise.

Hilbert et al. (2003) noted that massage reduces inflammation and DOMS. Massage guns, through percussive vibration, increase blood flow and ease post-exercise pain and stiffness.

Schneider et al., working with Truman State University, studied 28 athletes. Both manual massage and massage gun therapy reduced pain, but manual massage had better results 24 hours later and immediately improved hamstring ROM.

Davis et al. (2020) reported mixed results. While massage reduced DOMS-related pain by 13% and improved ROM by 7%, effects on muscle fatigue varied widely across studies.

Farr et al. (2002) found that manual massage (effleurage and petrissage) helped reduce DOMS after downhill running but did not improve muscle strength or function.

References

Davis, H.L., Alabed, S. and Chico, T.J. (2020) 'Effect of sports massage on performance and recovery: A systematic review and meta-analysis', *BMJ Open Sport & Exercise Medicine*, 6(1).

Farr, T., Nottle, C., Nosaka, K. and Sacco, P. (2002) 'The effects of therapeutic massage on delayed onset muscle soreness and muscle function following downhill walking', *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 5(4), pp. 297-306. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440\(02\)80018-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440(02)80018-4)

Conclusion

Drawing from a variety of peer-reviewed studies, the author established that both massage techniques offer measurable benefits in improving range of motion, flexibility, and in reducing muscle stiffness and soreness in the short term. Massage guns, particularly at low frequencies, were shown to have a slight advantage in immediate stiffness reduction and short-term recovery, while manual massage, particularly effleurage, demonstrated sustained benefits in pain relief and flexibility post-24 hours.

However, no definitive evidence emerged to suggest one method is categorically superior across all metrics. The studies reviewed also revealed considerable variability in methodology, sample groups, and assessment tools, most notably the reliance on subjective pain scales, which complicates drawing universal conclusions. Furthermore, limitations around inconsistent treatment protocols and the absence of long-term data further highlight the need for more rigorous, standardised research in this area.

To conclude, while both techniques are valuable tools for addressing DOMS in athletic and fitness settings, their effectiveness is highly individualised. Further research with consistent parameters and participant demographics is needed to better understand the full clinical implications of each treatment.

Zbigniew Ksiazak

A Holistic Approach To Improve Mental and Physical Health for 41 Years-Old Man.

University of Highlands and Islands

Introduction
This project presents a comprehensive 12-week wellness programme designed specifically for 41-year-old male, integrating strength training, cardiovascular conditioning, flexibility and mobility exercises, and mental health practices. The programme aims to enhance overall body function and long-term health through a balanced combination of physical activity, nutritional guidance, and stress management techniques

Aims of the project
1.To improve the physical health and fitness of a 41-years-old man through a balanced exercise and nutrition programme, enhancing strength, flexibility and overall vitality.
2. To promote mental health and emotional well-being by incorporating mindfulness, stress management techniques, and personal development practices, leading to better life balance and reduced anxiety.

Objectives of the project
1. Conduct a comprehensive assessment of the individual's current physical and mental health
2. Design a personalised physical wellness programme that includes a mix of aerobic exercises, strength training and flexibility routine.
3. Improve mental health, reduce stress, improve focus, and increase emotional resilience.
4. Improve sleep quality, and create routines that promotes self-care, and long-term health maintenance

Results

Blood Pressure And Resting Heart Rate

Pre-programme test- 151/88 –RHR 60 Week 12 of programme test - 116/85 –RHR-74

BLOOD PRESSURE CATEGORY	SYSTOLIC mm Hg (upper number)		DIASTOLIC mm Hg (lower number)
NORMAL	LESS THAN 120	and	LESS THAN 80
ELEVATED	120 – 129	and	LESS THAN 80
HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE (HYPERTENSION) STAGE 1	130 – 139	or	80 – 89
HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE (HYPERTENSION) STAGE 2	140 OR HIGHER	or	90 OR HIGHER
HYPERTENSIVE CRISIS (consult your doctor immediately)	HIGHER THAN 180	and/or	HIGHER THAN 120

BMI

Pre-programme test - BMI 40.5 Week 12 of the programme- BMI 35.4

Weight

Pre-programme test 116.9 kg Week 12 of the programme 102.4kg

Sit-and-Reach Test

Pre-programme test - -12 cm Week 12 of the programme – -3 cm

Agility T-Test

Pre-programme test 13.07 sec Week 12 of programme test – 11.90

Plank Test

Pre- programme test – 2.13 min Week 12 of programme test 3.16 min

Discussion and Conclusion

Tests and reports were available to assess the success of every objective, apart from sleeping quality, which does not suggest that improvements were not achieved, but there was no proof that they happened. To help the client manage the emotions and provide understanding of the interactions between emotional and rational parts of the brain The Chimp Paradox book by Steve Peters were recommended. The Chimp Paradox A Mind Management uses a simple analogy to help understand and take control of the emotions and act in individual's best interest whether it is in making decisions, communications with others or health and happiness

To improve flexibility and mobility, especially in hips area, PNF stretching were incorporated into the training routine after each session as well as Romanian Deadlift in main strength session to help strengthen the muscles in lower body and improve their flexibility.(Reznik (2024))

Literature Review

To target mindfulness and stress relief techniques, as stated by Woodyard (2011) in National Library of Medicine article, yoga is a form of mind-body fitness that involves a combination of muscular activity and an internally directed mindful focus on awareness of the self, the breath, and energy. Yoga improves body flexibility, promotes and improves respiratory and cardiovascular function as well as reduce stress, anxiety and improve sleep quality.

Recommendations

Recommendation for the client is to continue with the activities that worked well, especially the fitness routines and mindfulness practices, to maintain progress. Staying consistent with sleeping schedule and finding ways to better manage emotional outbursts will be key to making lasting changes

References

American College of Sports Medicine, (2014) Resource Manual for Guidance for Exercise Testing and Prescription, Muscular Fitness and Assessment, Sit-and-Reach Evaluation p368
 American College of Sports Medicine, (2011) Complete Guide to Fitness and Health, p153
 British Nutrition Foundation (2025), Recommendations For Men
 Reznik, M., (2024). The Romanian Deadlift. How to use it for pain, dysfunction and weakness.
 Woodyard, C., (2011) National Library of Medicine, Exploring the Therapeutic Effects of Yoga and Its Ability to Increase Quality of Life.

The Epidemiology of Injury in Horse Riders

University of Highlands and Islands

Introduction

Equestrian sport can be defined as activities completed on horseback, it is a sport that requires a combination of skill and horsemanship (*International Olympic Committee, 2024*). It is hypothesised to be more dangerous than motorcycling, skiing, football or rugby and therefore riders are susceptible to a lot of injuries (*Thompson et al., 2015*).

Aims of the project

The study aimed to investigate the study of occurrence, causes and effecting factors in injuries and conditions relating to horse riders (Institute of Medicine (US) and National Research Council (US) Committee on Trauma Research (1985, Section 2). The common mechanisms and injuries in horse riders; the prevalence of pain associated with horse riding; and the common conditions associated with horse riders were all explored.

Participants and Procedure

An anonymous online questionnaire was distributed using JISC and targeted horse riders in the local area as well as UK based riders both male and female, from ages 5 and upwards by using horse specific Facebook groups and Instagram tags. To meet the eligibility criteria, the participants must have participated in horse riding before; be UK based and volunteered the information of their own accord.

45 horse riders participated in the study (males= 4%; females= 96%; mean age range= 36 years old and over; mean years of riding experience= 21+ years). Most participants reported to ride between on average 0-7 hours of riding per week from multiple different disciplines. However, the most reported disciplines were hacking, dressage, showjumping and eventing; with hacking being the most prevalent. From the received responses, 49% of participants reported to classify themselves as amateur riders, 39% competitive amateurs, 29% low level rider and the remaining 7% professional rider.

Result

Graph 1: How the injury was sustained

Graph 2: Location of injury.

Graph 3: Aggravating factors of the reported injury.

Graph 4: Common pathologies and if they were worsened with horse riding/related activities.

Participants stated 40% had experienced some form of low-level pain when riding and described it as 'aching' or 'restricted' movement. When asked where they thought the pain came from participants gave a variety of answers from tight muscles, age or improper stirrup length however no clear trends were concluded from the data. A study by Lewis & Kennerley (2017) found 74% of elite dressage riders competed while experiencing pain.

Discussions and Conclusions

The common mechanisms and injuries seen in horse riders were head injuries, caused by falls from a horse and almost all injuries reported were classified as acute. From these injuries, 43% of participants reported that riding, 27% reported any movement (including breathing, sitting and lying), 16% reported the weather and 14% reported general yard activities (such as mucking out, grooming or handling) aggravated the injury (*Graph 3*). The prevalence of pain in horse riders ranged from 40-74% from studies examined, however from the nature of the sport and its vast age range as well as years of experience, especially at elite competitive levels pain is expected to be high. More investigation into prevalence of pain in amateur riders may be relevant for future studies. Common pathologies seen and worsened by horse riding concluded to involve the upper respiratory tract (asthma, allergies, hay fever) which could be hypothesised to be aggravated due to the environment in which keeping horses provides but more research may be required. A further 42% of participants stated their reported conditions only occurred when riding or completing a horse related activities.

Recommendations

To further improve the project, it is recommended the demographic be expanded to worldwide instead of UK based, and the sample size increased to a minimum of 100 participants to decrease the margin of error. Interviewing the participants could also improve the project due to the interviewer being able to clarify questions and get the participant to clarify answers. This may also remove some self-bias as they may be less likely to overexaggerate descriptions (*Sue & Ritter, 2016*).

References

Institute of Medicine (US) and National Research Council (US) Committee on Trauma Research (1985). *Injury In America: A Continuing Public Health Problem*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US)

International Olympic Committee (2024) *Equestrian: Olympic history, rules, latest updates and upcoming events for the Olympic sport, Olympics*. Available at: <https://olympics.com/en/sports/equestrian/> (Accessed: 11 November 2024).

Lewis, V., & Kennerley, R. (2017). A preliminary study to investigate the prevalence of pain in elite dressage riders during competition in the United Kingdom. *Comparative Exercise Physiology*, 13(4), 259–264. <https://doi.org/10.3920/cep170016>

Sue, V. M., & Ritter, L. A. (2016). *Conducting online surveys*. SAGE.

Thompson, K., McGreevy, P. and McManus, P. (2015) 'A critical review of horse-related risk: A research agenda for safer mounts, riders and equestrian cultures', *Animals*, 5(3), pp. 561–575. doi:10.3390/ani5030372.

Most Prevalent Injuries In Highland Dancing

Louise Robertson

University of Highlands and Islands

Introduction

Highland dancing carries a risk of injury. This project looks at the 2 most prevalent injuries sustained in Highland Dancing. The cause and how to prevent the injuries from occurring using with reference to biomechanics.

Biomechanical Insight Footwear and Surfaces

Ghillies, are the shoes worn in Highland dancing, they have little padding or support. Combined with hard, non-sprung floors, this increases impact on the tibia and Achilles tendon.

Shin Splints

These are caused by repeated toe landings and jumping (e.g., pas de basque, fling), which put stress on the tibia due to poor shock absorption and tired muscles.

Achilles Tendonitis

Occurs from overuse and repeated muscle contractions during jumps and moves like shedding. Weak or unsupportive footwear adds to the risk.

Movement Impact

Moves like pas de basque and shedding place weight on the toes, which puts extra strain on the tibia and Achilles tendon, leading to pain or inflammation.

Pas De Basque Shedding Behind Shedding Infront

Method

An online JISC survey of 21 dancers from the Sarah Hendry School of Dance found that 95% of reported injuries occurred during Highland dancing, with data on age, injury history, and treatments. Analysed in Excel under full ethical consent.

Results

The most Prevalent injuries of Highland Dancing are Shin Splints (57%) and Achilles Tendonitis (48%)

Dancers ranged in age from 5 to over 30, with most aged between 22–24. Although Premier dancers made up the majority of responses, many injuries had started earlier, during beginner or intermediate levels. Dancers reported that their injuries often began in childhood or teens and got worse with progression. There were no specific dances consistently linked to injuries, which suggests that overuse and repetitive movement, rather than individual routines, were the main causes.

Prevention Strategies

Eccentric heel drop exercises (Alfredson protocol) on stairs, or a step helps to support Achilles recovery. Strengthening key muscles like the tibialis posterior and gastrocnemius reduces strain on vulnerable areas, and helps dancers handle the repetitive forces involved. Include stretching and ensure a gradual return to dancing post-injury.

Orthotics are not suitable with ghillies, limiting support options,

Conclusion

Highland dancers are prone to overuse injuries, particularly shin splints and Achilles tendonitis. Improved education on biomechanics and targeted strengthening can reduce injury risk. Further research with larger, diverse samples is recommended.

References

(Bhusari & Deshmukh, 2023; O'Brien, 2005; Medina Pabón & Naqvi, 2023; Galbraith & Lavalley, 2009; van der Vlist et al., 2020)

Holly Berry Shotton¹

University of Highlands and Islands

Aim

To determine how gender influences hamstring flexibility.

Objective 1 – Investigate different ways of measuring hamstring flexibility and the resulting data from males and females.
Objective 2 – Assess anatomical differences in the different genders and its impact on flexibility. Objective 3 – Identify other physiological factors that could affect flexibility.

Introduction

Flexibility is defined as the range of motion around the joint and its ability to move the joint across the entire range of motion smoothly without any restrictions or pain (Cai, Liu and Li, 2023).

The hamstrings, situated on the posterior thigh, consist of the biceps femoris, semimembranosus, and semitendinosus muscles (Goulart, Ferreira and Navega, 2022). A lack of flexibility in this muscle group is well discussed and recognised as a common issue and a cause of injury (Afonso *et al*, 2021). Additionally, stretching can increase performance in sport (Song *et al*, 2018). The hamstrings are used during knee flexion and hip extension, and are a key muscle in sport, exercise, and everyday life to ensure proper function and mobility. This research will use secondary research methods to investigate what effect gender may have on the flexibility of the hamstrings. To better understand this, a systematic approach to the evidence will be used to better understand the characteristics which may influence this.

Results

There are many ways to **measure hamstring flexibility**. Some of these tests are Active knee extension (AKE), single leg raise (SLR), passive knee extension (PKE) and sit and reach (SR) test.

Allam *et al*, (2023) conducted tests on AKE, SLR and found a significant difference between males and females in hamstring flexibility. With SLR measuring the angle, females achieved a mean of 28.71° and males with a mean of 25.45°. They determined that **females have less** hamstring flexibility than males. This is **supported by Divyashri, Prathap and Preetha, (2021)** who also tested AKE on 27 females and 8 males and resulted in females having greater hamstring tightness. This study however is **contradicted** by both **Nagai *et al*, (2021)** and **Yu *et al*. (2022)** studies.

Youdas *et al*, (2005) concluded that **women have greater hamstring muscle length (HML)** than men, with men having approximately 8° less PSLR than women, and 11° less PA (popliteal angle) than women. However, this study is **contradicted** by **Wan *et al*. (2017)** concluding that males have longer hamstrings.

Eby *et al*, (2016) discovered that as **age increases the muscle stiffness increases**, however stiffness only starts to increase at an older age (60+). This is **contradicted** by **Youdas *et al*, (2005)** who deduced that there was no difference in HML as age increases, meaning that there is no change in flexibility. This is supported by Nagai *et al*, (2021)

Ferlin *et al*, (2016) discovered that relaxin has benefits for fibrotic musculoskeletal disorders as it helps improve tissue flexibility. This shows that individuals **with higher levels of relaxin** (which is common in females), have a **higher level of flexibility** throughout the body.

Miyazaki and Maeda, (2022) discovered that the **higher the levels of oestrogen** during ovulation the **decrease in muscle stiffness**. This means that females, compared to males, have a higher level of oestrogen with a more flexible range. This is **supported** by **Chidi-Ogbolu and Baar (2019)**

Key findings/ conclusion

Objective 1	There are inconclusive results on which gender is more flexible. However, the data leans to females being more flexible. More tests need to be done on hamstring flexibility to determine which gender is more flexible.
Objective 2	Literature generally suggests that females have attributes which increase flexibility, however there are limited studies that look into this subject.
Objective 3	The data is inconclusive on whether age affects flexibility. There was a lot of data which determines that hormones like oestrogen and relaxin increases flexibility. This suggests that females would have more flexibility than males as they have higher levels of these hormones than men.

Following a critical analysis of literature, it can be summarised females are more likely to be more flexible due to higher levels of oestrogen and relaxin, longer HML and an increased body temperature compared to males.

However, there are other factors that make it difficult to conclude, for example, what each participant does in their spare time that could affect their range of flexibility. Some recommendations for future studies are that they use larger sample sizes to gather more information, that they ensure all participants do similar types of activities and they are similar in age to ensure accurate comparison between the genders, limiting the variables.

Allam, N.M., Ebrahim, H.A., Ibrahim, A.M., Elneblawi, N.H., El-Sherbiny, M. and Fouda, K.Z. (2023) 'The association of hamstring tightness with lumbar lordosis and trunk flexibility in healthy individuals: gender analysis.' *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 11, 1225973 Available from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10538639/> [Accessed: 28/04/25]

Youdas, J.W., Krause, D.A., Hollman, J.H., Harmsen, W.S. and Laskowski, E. (2005) 'The influence of gender and age on hamstring muscle length in healthy adults.' *Journal of Orthopaedic & Physical Therapy* 35(4), 246–252 Available from <https://www.jospt.org/doi/epdf/10.2519/jospt.2005.35.4.246> [Accessed: 29/04/25]

Miyazaki, M. and Maeda, S. (2022) 'Changes in hamstring flexibility and muscle strength during the menstrual cycle in healthy young females.' *Journal of Physical Therapy Science* 34(2), 92–98 Available from https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jpts/34/2/34_2021-1471_article [Accessed: 29/04/25]

Chidi-Ogbolu, N. and Baar, K. (2019) 'Effect of oestrogen on musculoskeletal performance and injury risk.' *Frontiers in Physiology* 15. Available from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6341375/> [Accessed: 29/04/25]

Cowdenbeath FC Mentorship and Professional Placement

Glen Addison, Gavin Moir, Thea Sinclair and Daniel Biggs

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1

2

Mentorship Evaluation

- Completion of 9-item questionnaire in the first week (early January)
Included questions about Confidence, Abilities and Beliefs and goal setting
Scale of 1 low - 4 high
Average Score 24/36
- Completion of the same 9-item questionnaire in the last week (mid April)
Average Score 33/36

Thus, an increase of 9 points across Confidence, Abilities and Beliefs during the mentorship

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3

The Mentorship/Placement provided me with:

- “Vital inside knowledge and experience on the workings of a football club. I got to speak with players about their injuries and discuss how best to rehabilitate them”.
- “A supervised space to help grow my therapist knowledge and become more confident in assessing injuries. I had the ability to ask questions during assessments and while providing treatment”.

I have learned:

- “How to set up pitch-side as a sports therapist, and how to deal with acute injuries using massage techniques and exercise options”.
- “Different ways to assess injuries depending on the space available”.
- “What the common football injuries are and how to rehab them”.

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4

Interpretation

- Throughout this placement, I experienced what life as a Sports Therapist at a football club is about, I learned different ways to assess and treat injuries that football players experience. I was able to enhance my knowledge through learning on the job compared to always being in a classroom.
- At the start of the placement, I lacked confidence in assessing and treating the athletes due to inexperience, but as time went on, I got more confident in my abilities in assessing and treating the athletes, and by the end of it, I felt I could do it alone.

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Conclusion

- The whole experience is very valuable, it can be used as a springboard into the field of Sports Therapy, and I now feel so much more confident going into future placements or jobs at football clubs.
- In conclusion, I gained a lot of valuable experience and knowledge of what it's like working as a sports therapist as part of a team, and I now have a better understanding of what tasks I may face and ways to work efficiently.

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Presentation References (Harvard)

How to reference included Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health work

Addison, G, Moir, G, Sinclair, T, and Biggs, D., 2025. *Cowdenbeath FC Mentorship and Professional Placement* [Oral presentation]. UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health, Perth, Scotland, 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Chervonnaia, S., 2025. Efficacy of strength training on flexibility and cardiovascular endurance on a young adult. Does Sport Improve Mental Wellbeing? [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Innes, J., 2025. To investigate the effectiveness of soft tissue therapy massage techniques versus Deep Tissue Massage Gun techniques on active/fitness enthusiasts dealing with Delayed Onset Muscle Soreness post-activity. [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Ksiazak, Z., 2025. A Holistic Approach To Improve Mental and Physical Health for 41 Years-Old Man. [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

McCrindle, E., 2025. The Epidemiology of Injury in Horse Riders [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Robertson, L., 2025. Most Prevalent Injuries In Highland Dancing [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Shotton, B. H., 2025. How gender influences hamstring flexibility [Poster] *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Perth, Scotland 2 June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

Conference Proceedings Harvard reference:

Biggs, D. (ed.) 2025. Proceeding of the UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health. *UHI Perth Student Conference: Sport, Fitness and Health*. Held 2nd June 2025 at Perth Scotland. UHI Perth: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15540312

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